

Stress–strain curves and derived mechanical parameters of P91 steel from spherical nanoindentation at a range of temperatures

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HIGHLIGHTS

- Force-displacement curves of spherical indentations show similar hardness profiles independent of the measurement method.
- Hardness of P91 decreases by a factor of three from RT to 600 °C as measured by both quasi-static and dynamic indentations.
- The accuracy of the contact stiffness measurement is critical to reach realistic ISSC using Hertz model of contact mechanics.
- Similar tensile properties are extracted from quasi-static and dynamic spherical nanoindentation at slow strain rates.

GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

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ABSTRACT

This work compares different measurement and analysis protocols of spherical nanoindentation tests performed at different temperatures on a ferritic/martensitic P91 grade steel, in order to derive meaningful indentation stress–strain curves (ISSC) and estimate material parameters such as indentation modulus, yield strength, work hardening exponent and ultimate tensile strength. Quasi-static multi-cycle and dynamic continuous stiffness measurement indentation using a spherical indenter with a tip radius of 20 μm has been carried out from room temperature to 600 °C in vacuum in a set-up where thermal drift has been minimised by an active surface referencing system and accurate temperature stabilization in the contact area. The methodology used to determine the contact radius is critical to achieve consistent results. The application of different combinations of definitions of contact radius and indentation-induced strain to nanoindentation data obtained by the quasi-static and dynamic measurements reveals that Tabor's approach combined with a geometrically determined contact radius best represents the ISSC relationship for the P91 characterized. This method is then extended to predict the high temperature tensile properties of the steel from nanoindentation results.

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1. Introduction

The tensile properties of metallic materials constitute the key material specifications needed for structural design. Young's modulus, yield

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stress, work hardening rate and ultimate tensile strength (UTS) derive from plots of engineering stress versus strain, usually measured by uniaxial tensile testing. However, to produce conventional tensile test pieces according to pertinent standards, the material has to be available in sufficiently large volumes, which can be prohibitive, for instance in the case of ion irradiated material where only superficial layers of micrometer-sized depth are affected. Nanoindentation, on the other hand, can probe very shallow depths, even in the order of a few tens of nanometers, and still provide reproducible measurements of near-surface stress–strain curves. Nanoindentation allows extracting local mechanical properties from small regions of interest, such as welds, coatings or ion-irradiated layers. For self-similar pyramidal and conical indenters, a characteristic strain exists which is independent of the indentation depth and proportional to the tangent of the angle between the longitudinal axis and the side face of the indenter. Much effort has been made to extract information from self-similar indentations additional to local hardness and reduced modulus, notably by applying the analytical expanding cavity models [1–3] that aim at providing information on the flow stress [4]. However, information about the stress–strain behaviour can only be obtained by varying the tip opening angle to probe stress at a range of strain values. Unlike those self-similar tips, for spherical indenter tips, the contact angle varies with indentation depth and therefore the strain induced by the tip is a function of depth. Probing the surface with spherical tips combined with various data analysis procedures allows deriving the elastic-plastic behaviour of the material under test, from the initial elastic response during loading, to the onset of plasticity and the post-yield behaviour [5–8]. This can then be applied to quantify the degradation of surface layers, i.e. ion-irradiated layers [9]. Such data, together with an analysis of the microstructure at the indentation site, can also provide critical information for the validation of physics-based multiscale models of materials ageing.

Spherical indentation has the advantage of enabling a continuous change of the mean pressure and characteristic strain as the indenter advances into the material. While significant refinements in the measurement protocols have been achieved, the conversion of spherical force–displacement curves to indentation stress–strain curves (ISSC) is still an open issue since a robust mathematical relation between the force–displacement curve and an equivalent indentation stress–strain curve is not known [10]. Recent studies have presented alternative ways of defining contact radius and representative strain, and finite element models predicted quite different ISSC depending on the definitions [11,12]. The contact radius can be determined from a geometrical relationship between radius and depth or from Hertz model describing the contact mechanics between two elastic solids with spherical surfaces. Representative strains can be derived via the classic Tabor formulation assuming proportionality of strain and the ratio of contact radius over tip radius [13], or from the Pathak-Kalidindi model [11,14] where strain is assumed proportional to depth over contact radius.

High chromium ferritic/martensitic (F/M) steels containing 9–12 wt% Cr are candidate materials for structural components in future fusion and fission nuclear reactors, in particular for reactor components where high temperature strength, and corrosion and/or irradiation resistance are critical, for instance, for steam generators or in-core components [15]. P91 grade materials are 9 wt% Cr high-strength F/M steels that exhibit outstanding void swelling resistance, good mechanical performance in terms of tensile and creep strength and fatigue life at high temperatures, as well as good high-temperature corrosion resistance.

This work analyses quasi-static and dynamic spherical nanoindentation measurement of P91 at high temperatures with the aim of developing a methodology for obtaining equivalent tensile properties based on different approaches for the generation of stress–strain curves; notably different methods for determining contact area and representative strain. In order to identify an appropriate methodology, indentation tensile properties (yield stress, tensile stress and work hardening) are evaluated by fitting a constitutive equation to the indentation stress–strain data, extracting equivalent tensile properties from high temperature nanoindentation, and comparing them with known tensile properties. This is to prepare the ground for extending the methodology to the derivation of constitutive properties of layers of steels subjected to superficial ion irradiation damage with unknown bulk tensile properties.

2. Experimental

2.1. Materials

The chemical composition of the P91 (9Cr1MoVNB type) F/M steel used in this study is given in Table 1. Chromium is added to improve high temperature strength, and corrosion and oxidation resistance, while molybdenum is used to increase creep resistance. The specimens were cut from a hot rolled plate, produced by Industeel, normalized at 1060 °C during 4 h, quenched in water to room temperature, tempered at 760 °C for 3 h 20 min then cooled in air. The yield stress and UTS of the as-produced P91 plate were 522 MPa and 684 MPa, respectively, in terms of engineering stresses. The material was cut into cylinders of 25 mm diameter and 2 mm thickness and polished with successively finer grinders and polishing solutions finalising by a gentle polishing in oxide polishing suspension (OPS with silica nanoparticles) for 5 min. The typical ferritic/martensitic microstructure of P91 is shown in Fig. 1 (a). The fine martensite structure consists of laths of several hundreds of nm in size, which govern the micro-mechanical response of the material. The striated structure of martensite laths can be seen in the SEM micrographs, while the texture of the coarser pre-austenite grain precursor of the martensite phase can still be perceived in the EBSD inverse pole figures (Fig. 1 (b)).

2.2. Ambient and high temperature nanoindentation testing

Indentation tests were conducted in an ultra-nanoindenter test machine, UNHT³-HTV from Anton Paar, featuring active top surface referencing that minimises thermal drift and improves measurement stability. The system consists of an indentation head and two imaging heads (AFM and optical microscope) and a motorised stage to transport the sample from the imaging heads to the indenter. The measuring head, sample stage and optical microscope are mounted in a high vacuum chamber, which prevents oxidation and tip degradation during high temperature testing. The indenter tip, reference tip and sample are heated separately by infrared heating elements and the test temperature is monitored by thermocouples welded to the tips. The sample is fixed to the holder by means of a retaining ring, which clamps it rigidly, thus removing the need to use glue or cement. In this configuration, the frame compliance was 0.57 µm/N. A detailed description of the instrument can be found in Ref. [16].

A sphero-conical (20 µm tip radius, 90° cone angle) indenter tip from tungsten carbide, WC, was used for the indentation tests. WC has a

Table 1
Chemical composition of P91 (in wt% unless otherwise indicated; Fe balance).

Element	Cr	Mo	Mn	Si	V	Ni	Nb	Cu	Al	C	N
%	8.32	1.02	0.41	0.24	0.235	0.10	0.084	0.05	0.006	0.12	0.041
Element	P	S	Sn	W	Ti	As	Sb	Zr	B	O	
%	0.0091	0.001	0.005	0.001	0.002	0.005	0.001	0.001	0.0009	15 ppm	

Fig. 1. SEM (a) and EBSD (b) images showing ferritic/martensitic structure of P91.

lower hardness than diamond but exhibits higher stability and chemical inertia in contact with other materials at high temperature. The Young's modulus of WC is reported to remain constant at around 700 GPa up to 600 °C [17]. Nanoindentation tests at room temperature, 200 °C, 400 °C and 600 °C were applied using quasi-static and dynamic measurement modes. Ten measurements spaced at intervals of 50 μm were carried out at room temperature, while three to eight good measurements were obtained at high temperature with a distance of 100 μm between indents. Quasi-static nanoindentation was performed in multicycle mode (MC) applying 20 cycles with quadratic force increase up to 100 mN, unloading to 50% of the maximum force of the cycle, loading/unloading time of 10 s and 5 s dwell at maximum force for each cycle.

A nanoindentation study conducted on similar F/M materials using Berkovich indenters and CSM mode at several oscillation parameters (10–100 Hz and 5–20 mN) [18] had shown that the dynamic measurements performed at 20 Hz and 5 mN provided closest results to quasi-static measurements, noting a strong dependence of indentation size effects on the oscillation parameters. In the present study, dynamic nanoindentation was performed using force-controlled continuous stiffness measurements (CSM), superimposing a sinusoidal oscillation of 20 Hz frequency and 5 mN amplitude to a base load increasing at constant strain rate of 0.05 s⁻¹, 0.01 s⁻¹ and 0.1 s⁻¹ up to 100 mN. The displacement amplitude measured at the end of the loading segment was about 2 nm at room temperature. The amplitude of the oscillation was low enough to assume linear unloading [19] while still being resolved by the measurement system. The surface was detected from the contact stiffness signal. The zero-load and zero-displacement point was determined from a contact stiffness increase above 300 μN/μm. Fig. 2 (a) and (b) illustrate real-time force-displacement curves recorded applying the MC and CSM method at room temperature, respectively.

To achieve thermal stabilization for high temperature measurements, the thermal bath created between the two tips and the sample needs to be equilibrated. First, the probes and sample are heated up close to the target temperature and allowed to stabilise in servo-loop mode. Then the temperature of the reference tip is adjusted to match the sample temperature by releasing the temperature feedback loop, bringing the reference into contact with the surface and minimising the temperature gradient between reference tip and sample surface. The temperature of the indenter tip is then adjusted by the same equilibration procedure. Finally, thermal drift is corrected by using a 5 min dwell at 10% of the maximum force and fine-tuning the indenter temperature to achieve a constant depth. When all three elements are in thermal equilibrium, a matrix of MC and CSM measurements is launched.

MC data were analysed according to ISO 14577-1: 2015 by fitting the 98% to 40% of maximum force (F_{max}) portion of the unloading curve of each cycle to a power law and using the fitted parameters to calculate the contact depth h_c , the contact radius a and area $A_c = \pi a^2$, the contact stiffness S , and indentation hardness $H_{IT} = F_{max}/A_c$.

CSM data analysis has been performed assuming an elastic deformation response to the oscillatory loading and dynamically calculating the sample stiffness and the indentation contact depth by applying a gliding average of five periods per point.

S and h_c calculated from force-displacement curves are used as inputs for the derivation of indentation stress-strain curves (ISSCs) to infer the mechanical parameters of indentation yield stress and indentation work hardening exponent, from which an estimate of an apparent UTS from nanoindentation can be extracted. This derivation involves three steps [20]:

- (1) the *determination of the contact area* can be done either (a) by using the geometrical relationship of a spherical cap to calculate the geometrically-based contact radius $a_{geom} = \sqrt{2h_c R_i - h_c^2}$ as a function of the indenter radius R_i , or (b) by using Hertz' contact mechanics formulation for two elastic spheres in contact for the stiffness-based contact radius $a_{Hertz} = S/(2E_r)$, where E_r denotes the reduced elastic modulus. S derives from the slope of the unloading curve in quasi-static nanoindentation or from the continuous stiffness measurement signal in dynamic mode of the indentation response, which are both assumed purely elastic.
- (2) the *definition of representative stress and strain* values can (a) either be based on the relations proposed by Tabor [13], namely $\sigma_{IT} \approx H_{IT}/3$ with an empirical constraint factor of (approximately) 3 for fully plastic behaviour, and an empirical strain $\varepsilon_{Tabor} \approx 0.2 a/R$, or (b) the more recent definition of a representative strain proposed by Pathak et al. [11,14] $\varepsilon_{Pathak} = 4 h_t/(3\pi a)$ depending on the total penetration depth h_t at peak force for each unloading cycle or, respectively, the depth measured in dynamic mode.
- (3) The *quantitative evaluation of the indentation tensile properties* entails fitting the indentation stress-strain curve to a straight line for the initial elastic loading and to a constitutive equation describing the plastic deformation for which a simple power-law is assumed here. An apparent elastic modulus E can be determined from the contact stiffness or from the slope of the linear fit of the initial elastic portion of the ISSC. The yield stress is conveniently defined in analogy to the proof stress $R_{p0.2}$ as the intercept of the experimental data curve with the initial linear elastic regime given by a linear curve with slope equal to E and shifted 0.2% in strain ε_{IT} :

$$\sigma_{y,IT} = E (\varepsilon_{y,IT} - 0.002) \quad (1)$$

here $\varepsilon_{y,IT}$ is the strain at the intersection between the offset line and the data curve.

Fig. 2. Room-temperature NI force displacement curves for P91 measured by MC (a) and CSM using a constant strain rate of 0.1 s^{-1} (b).

Grade 91 steels can be considered power-law hardening materials, for which the plastic segment of the true ISSC can be fitted to the simple constitutive equation

$$\sigma_{IT} = K \varepsilon_{IT}^{n_{IT}} \quad (2)$$

here K is the strength coefficient and n_{IT} is the indentation work-hardening exponent. The indentation ultimate tensile stress UTS_{IT} and engineering strain at UTS_{IT} are then calculated by:

$$UTS_{IT} = K \left(\frac{n_{IT}}{e} \right)^{n_{IT}} \quad (3)$$

$$\varepsilon_{UTS_{IT}}^{eng} = e^{n_{IT}} - 1 \quad (4)$$

It is recalled that UTS is a notion from tensile testing, referring to the true stress at which the strain hardening rate is balanced by the cross section reduction rate, causing a maximum of the engineering stress and the onset of necking. While this process is not relevant in compressive indentation mode of testing, fitting of n_{IT} and K is going to allow one to access indirectly those tensile properties, to quantify equivalent properties, and to assess benefits and limitations of the presently adopted methodologies.

3. Results

The force–displacement curves have been converted into indentation stress–strain curves by applying the two relationships of contact radius, namely the geometrical one and the stiffness-based expression from Hertz' model of contact mechanics. Moreover, the two definitions of representative strain from the empirical Tabor's relation and from Pathak and Kalidindi's more recent proposal have been adopted, resulting in four different combinations [11,14].

Fig. 3 compares the hardness (a) and stiffness profiles (b) obtained from force–displacement curves recorded using multicycle versus continuous stiffness measurements done at a constant strain rate of 0.01 s^{-1} . The data points in the multicycle graphs stem from the average, cycle by cycle, of the parameters of the power law fitting to the partial unloading segments of five measurements, while the CSM hardness and stiffness curves have been plotted from the average of the continuous measurement of stiffness at constant strain rate of 0.01 s^{-1} . The agreement of the complementary hardness and stiffness measurement results from the quasi-static and the dynamic method is noted to be very good.

A reduced modulus $E_{eff} = 177 \text{ GPa}$ results from the elastic modulus of P91 [21], $E_s = 212 \text{ GPa}$, and Poisson ratio $\nu_s = 0.3$, while the

Fig. 3. Hardness (a) and stiffness (b) profiles as a function of contact depth of P91 measured by spherical nanoindentation in continuous multi-cycling mode and continuous stiffness measurement mode using a constant strain rate of 0.01 s^{-1} .

corresponding properties of the WC indenter tip are $E_i = 700$ GPa and $\nu_i = 0.24$. Fig. 4 shows the ISSCs which have then been reconstructed using the four combinations for the determination of contact radius and representative strain again from force-displacement curves recorded using multicycle (a, b) and continuous stiffness (c, d) measurements.

It is noted that Tabor's and Pathak's formulations of strain differ with respect to an offset and renormalization of strain, which is less pronounced for the geometrical contact radius. The way of determining the contact radius, however, is critical even for the qualitative appearance of the graphs analysed: the stiffness-based calculation of the contact radius (a_{Hertz}) induces an increasing hardening rate deep in the plastic deformation regime which is why power-law fits have not been applied in this case (Fig. 4 (b)). The accuracy in determining the contact stiffness as a function of depth strongly affects the uncertainties of results when the Hertz model of the contact radius is used.

In the case of dynamic measurements, a strong dependence of the contact stiffness on the harmonic parameters and notably on the loading rate in constant strain rate measurements has been reported [22]. Deviations in stiffness were higher at the largest indentation depths because the force rate increases exponentially as indentation progresses at

constant strain rate [22]. This may be the reason for the divergence of the dynamic ISSC at the largest strains (Fig. 4 (d)), which becomes more pronounced as the strain rate is increased (plot not shown).

Indentation tensile properties have been extracted according to Eqs. (1-4) from the ISSC, the results of which are shown in Fig. 5 and compiled in Table 2, specifying also the macro-scale tensile properties for comparison. Error estimates included in Table 2 are based on the error propagation from the uncertainties of the parameters providing best fits of the ISSC to linear elastic and power law flow curves. The combination of MC and stiffness based contact radius (Fig. 4 (b)) produced large errors in the elastic modulus determination from the initial data points of the curves and therefore the properties have not been extracted.

For both MC and CSM measurement modes, the geometry-based calculation of contact radius provides a more realistic representation of the ISSC and extracted indentation tensile properties, as compared to stiffness-based contact radius. The dynamic CSM measurements did not improve the results as compared to MC. The CSM measurements taken at the slowest strain rate have been used for the comparison, as these may show the smallest bias in the stiffness signal due to fast strain rate [22]. Indentation tensile properties were similar, but the elastic

Fig. 4. Indentation stress—strain curves of P91 derived from quasi-static multi-cycle nanoindentation (a, b) and from continuous stiffness measurements at constant strain rate of 0.01 s^{-1} (c, d) using geometrically-based (a, c) and stiffness-based (b, d) contact radius for both Tabor's and Pathak's formulations of strain.

Fig. 5. Fitting linear elastic and power-law plastic behaviour to ISSCs and derivation of apparent elastic modulus E , indentation yield stress $\sigma_{y,IT}$, indentation work-hardening exponent n_{IT} , and strength coefficient K . (a, b) have been obtained from multi-cycle spherical nanoindentation and (c – f) from continuous stiffness measurements at constant strain rate of 0.01 s^{-1} . The legend inside each graph shows the criteria used for defining contact radius and representative strain.

Table 2

Indentation tensile properties of P91 extracted from room temperature spherical nanoindentations performed in quasi-static continuous multi-cycle and in dynamic continuous stiffness measurement modes. The macroscale tensile properties of elastic modulus, yield stress and ultimate tensile strength, as well as the hardening exponent and strength coefficient are also listed.

		E [GPa]	$\sigma_{y,IT}$ [MPa]	n_{IT}	K [MPa]	UTS [MPa]	$\epsilon_{UTS, IT}$
MC	$a(h_c, R_i)$ $\epsilon \sim a/R$	167 ± 1	393 ± 39	0.202 ± 0.024	1201 ± 89	710 ± 80	0.22 ± 0.03
	$a(h_c, R_i)$ $\epsilon \sim h/a$	67 ± 7	383 ± 38	0.212 ± 0.017	1212 ± 65	706 ± 56	0.24 ± 0.02
CSM 0.01 s^{-1}	$a(h_c, R_i)$ $\epsilon \sim a/R$	130 ± 7	422 ± 42	0.275 ± 0.004	1509 ± 17	804 ± 13	0.32 ± 0.01
	$a(h_c, R_i)$ $\epsilon \sim h/a$	68 ± 1	408 ± 41	0.267 ± 0.003	1426 ± 13	767 ± 10	0.310 ± 0.004
	$a(S, E_{eff})$ $\epsilon \sim a/R$	74 ± 10	807 ± 81	0.048 ± 0.008	1083 ± 35	892 ± 51	0.05 ± 0.01
	$a(S, E_{eff})$ $\epsilon \sim h/a$	70 ± 6	788 ± 79	0.057 ± 0.009	1079 ± 34	866 ± 50	0.06 ± 0.01
	Macroscopic tensile test properties	212	522	0.095	940	684	0.10

Fig. 6. Hardness profiles as a function of contact depth of P91 measured at room temperature and at 200°C, 400 °C and 600 °C by spherical nanoindentation in continuous multi-cycling and continuous stiffness measurement modes at various constant strain rates.

modulus appears poorly determined by CSM, as it is largely underestimated. This can be due to intrinsic dependencies of the CSM method on material parameters (E/H ratio), on the parameters of the harmonic oscillation (frequency and amplitude), on the above-mentioned fast loading rate, but most importantly due to the strain dependence of the constraint factor [22], cf. Discussion below.

We observe that MC measurements analysed in terms of the geometrical definition of the contact radius and Tabor's formulae provide the best estimation of tensile properties, noting that the elastic modulus is accurate to 21%, the yield stress is underestimated by 25% and the UTS is slightly overestimated by 4%.

The analysis has been extended to high temperature measurements at 200 °C, 400 °C and 600 °C. Fig. 6 shows the calculated mean hardness profiles as a function of contact depth for the whole temperature range including room temperature for multicycle and continuous stiffness measurements at constant strain rates of 0.01 s^{-1} , 0.05 s^{-1} and 0.1 s^{-1} . The curves are mean curves of three to six measurements in the case of CSM, while for MC the curves have been plotted from the values of hardness obtained from the unloading portions of three to five force-displacement curves, averaged cycle by cycle. Similar hardness profiles were observed for the different testing methods, with the MC results matching closely the CSM results obtained for the lowest strain rate (0.01 s^{-1}). While the material is losing significantly in

Fig. 7. Indentation stress–strain curves of P91 derived from quasi-static multi-cycle spherical nanoindentation at room temperature and at 200°C, 400 °C and 600 °C using geometrically-based (a) and stiffness-based (b) contact radius determination for both Tabor's and Pathak's formulations of strain.

Fig. 8. Fitting linear elastic and power-law plastic behaviour to ISSCs obtained from multi-cycle nanoindentation of P91 at 200°C (a, b), 400 °C (c, d) and 600 °C (e, f). The values of apparent elastic modulus E , indentation yield stress $\sigma_{y,IT}$, indentation work-hardening exponent n_{IT} , and strength coefficient K , have been extracted using the geometrically-based definition of the contact radius and Tabor's (a, c, e) or Pathak's (b, d, f) representative strains.

Fig. 9. Compilation of indentation stress–strain curves of P91 derived from spherical nanoindentation performed at room temperature, 2000°C, 400°C and 600°C using continuous stiffness measurement mode at different constant strain rates, geometrically-based contact radius determination and Tabor's definition of strain. Curves represent averages of 5 to 10 measurements.

strength with increasing temperature, CSM nanoindentation curves at intermediate temperature, 200 °C, evidence plastic instability due to the dynamic strain ageing of the steel [23]. This is visible as a characteristic serrated yielding and an inverse strain rate dependence of the hardness being lowest for the highest strain rate of 0.1 s⁻¹ at 200 °C.

Fig. 7 shows the ISSCs deriving from the different ways of calculating contact radius and representative strain for the case of the MC measurements. It is obvious from Fig. 7 (b) that the stiffness-based determination of contact radius worsens at elevated temperatures to an extent that it cannot be used to extract meaningful equivalent tensile properties. Fitting the ISSCs to linear elastic and power-law plastic deformation behaviour was successful, however, for the geometrical definition of contact radius and both Tabor's and Pathak-Kalidindi's definitions of strain, noting that few data points are available to fit the elastic regime. Fig. 8 shows the fit results for the MC measurements at 200 °C to 600 °C. Only small differences are observed in the fit parameters for the Tabor and Pathak-Kalidindi formulation, noting that the elastic modulus is again largely underestimated by the latter. This is partly because the

strains are stretched, as compared to Tabor's formulation, generating a smaller slope of the elastic segment in the ISSC.

In the case of CSM have ISSCs been constructed from individual measurements at the different strain rates and then averaged to obtain a mean ISSC for each strain rate and testing temperature (Fig. 9). Fitting to extract indentation tensile properties has been applied to the mean curves. In view of the results at room temperature, only the case of the geometrical contact radius combined with Tabor's strain formulation has been used in the analysis of the high temperature CSM data. Table 3 summarises the values of the indentation tensile properties obtained from the different analyses at ambient and elevated temperatures for the case of geometrical contact radius and Tabor's strain. The values of E and UTS improve for CSM as the strain rate decreases, but quantitatively E remains poorly reproduced by dynamic measurements as compared to MC.

4. Discussion

Keeping in mind that the geometrical definition of the contact radius leads to much more robust results for the definitions of strain, as compared to the stiffness-based Hertzian contact mechanics, we now have to assess the performance of the ISSC generation with respect to stress, strain and strain-rate effects. Fig. 10 shows the temperature dependence of the yield stress and UTS up to 600 °C as extracted from ISSCs obtained by multicycle and dynamic measurements at different strain rates. A strong decrease in yield stress from RT to 600 °C by about a factor of three is observed, while UTS exhibits a weak temperature dependence up to 400 °C and then decreases significantly.

The T dependence of the UTS of P91 is very well predicted by the MC measurements within the limits of confidence. Also the CSM measurements at the lowest strain rate provide reasonable (20%) accuracy for UTS, while its strain-rate dependence is overestimated resulting in significantly overestimated UTS levels for the higher strain rates (Fig. 10). The pronounced strain rate dependence of UTS_{IT} from the CSM data at room temperature and 200 °C vanishes at 400 °C. This relates to the inverse strain-rate sensitivity of the flow stress, which is attributed to dynamic strain ageing [23] (cf. Fig. 6) and which also becomes manifest by the vanishing temperature dependence of the tensile flow stress in Fig. 10 and strain-rate softening instability governing the tensile tests performed at 375 °C, cf. Ref. [24].

The situation is different for the yield stress. Here the strain-rate dependence is realistic, resulting in close agreement of the MC measurements and the dynamic measurements at different strain rates, while the predicted yield stresses are systematically underestimated. This

Table 3

Indentation tensile properties of P91 extracted from spherical nanoindentation at room and high temperatures performed in quasi-static multi-cycle mode and in dynamic continuous stiffness measurement mode at different strain rates. The values have been extracted using the geometrical relationship for the determination of contact radius and Tabor's definition of representative strain.

	$a(h_c, R_i) \varepsilon \sim a/R$	E [GPa]	$\sigma_{y,IT}$ [MPa]	n_{IT}	K [MPa]	UTS [MPa]	$\varepsilon_{UTS, IT}$
RT	CSM 0.01 s ⁻¹	130 ± 7	422 ± 42	0.275 ± 0.004	1509 ± 17	804 ± 13	0.32 ± 0.01
	CSM 0.05 s ⁻¹	65.2 ± 0.4	405 ± 41	0.308 ± 0.005	1748 ± 27	894 ± 19	0.36 ± 0.01
	CSM 0.1 s ⁻¹	48 ± 1	400 ± 40	0.499 ± 0.013	3148 ± 109	990 ± 59	0.40 ± 0.02
200 °C	MC	167 ± 1	393 ± 39	0.202 ± 0.024	1201 ± 89	710 ± 80	0.22 ± 0.03
	CSM 0.01 s ⁻¹	116 ± 5	358 ± 36	0.192 ± 0.003	1091 ± 9	656 ± 9	0.210 ± 0.004
	CSM 0.05 s ⁻¹	69.3 ± 0.3	321 ± 32	0.300 ± 0.004	1580 ± 18	816 ± 13	0.35 ± 0.01
400 °C	CSM 0.1 s ⁻¹	69 ± 1	293 ± 29	0.335 ± 0.003	1823 ± 17	904 ± 11	0.400 ± 0.004
	MC	174 ± 17	346 ± 35	0.179 ± 0.018	1036 ± 66	637 ± 60	0.20 ± 0.02
	CSM 0.01 s ⁻¹	81.5 ± 0.3	207 ± 21	0.365 ± 0.001	1710 ± 7	822 ± 4	0.440 ± 0.001
600 °C	CSM 0.05 s ⁻¹	45.4 ± 0.2	247 ± 25	0.341 ± 0.001	1599 ± 7	788 ± 4	0.410 ± 0.001
	CSM 0.1 s ⁻¹	70.3 ± 0.4	228 ± 23	0.342 ± 0.001	1639 ± 4	807 ± 3	0.410 ± 0.001
	MC	80 ± 31	227 ± 27	0.262 ± 0.024	1190 ± 103	645 ± 77	0.30 ± 0.03
600 °C	CSM 0.01 s ⁻¹	13.5 ± 0.2	106 ± 11	0.424 ± 0.003	894 ± 7	407 ± 4	0.530 ± 0.004
	CSM 0.05 s ⁻¹	18.4 ± 0.1	115 ± 12	0.423 ± 0.005	1014 ± 1	462 ± 2	0.53 ± 0.01
	CSM 0.1 s ⁻¹	25.9 ± 0.1	116 ± 12	0.446 ± 0.001	1163 ± 4	519 ± 2	0.560 ± 0.002
	MC	21 ± 2	100 ± 10	0.415 ± 0.027	825 ± 60	378 ± 36	0.51 ± 0.04

Fig. 10. (a) Indentation yield stress, σ_{yIT} , and (b) ultimate tensile stress, UTS_{IT} , of P91 as functions of temperature measured by spherical nanoindentation using quasi-static multi-cycling and continuous stiffness measurements at different strain rates. σ_{yIT} and UTS_{IT} have been extracted using the geometrical relationship for the contact radius and Tabor's definition of representative strain. Tensile test data from Ref. [24] are shown for comparison.

effect becomes more pronounced as temperature increases resulting in yield stress falling short by 25% at room temperature and even 60% at 600 °C. The present findings, notably the high temperature results, are in contrast to reports according to which both the yield stress and the tensile strength derive from using a constant constraint factor of $C = 3$, see for instance [25] where better than $\pm 10\%$ accuracy is claimed for room temperature data of various steels and Al alloys.

The fact that UTS levels are well predicted, while yield stresses are not, rather points at a significant strain and temperature dependence of the constraint factor as the predominant source of error. In fact, a constraint factor $C \approx 3$ is only applicable sufficiently deep in the plastic regime independent of temperature, while it is significantly lower, here ranging from $C \approx 2.3$ at room temperature down to $C \approx 1.3$ at 600 °C, in the elastic-plastic transition regime. This is also reflected by too large apparent hardening exponents n_{IT} , in particular those deriving from CSM (Table 3). The variation of C during the transition from elastic to fully plastic deformation has been described through finite element analysis by Park and Pharr [26], as well as through comparison with uni-axial micro-pillar compression data by Merle et al. [22].

Strains determined by Pathak's expression are larger than those by Tabor's, especially for the stiffness-based contact radius. Fig. 4 (a, c) shows, however, that the strains based on the geometrical relationship but evaluated according to the different proposals by Tabor, and by Pathak and Kalidindi almost coincide, contrary to what was presented in their references [11, 14]. This implies.

$$\varepsilon_{IT} = 0.2 \frac{a}{R_i} \approx \frac{4 h_t}{3 \pi a} \text{ or } a^2 \approx \frac{20}{3\pi} h_t R_i,$$

which for geometrical reasons according to $a = \sqrt{2h_c R_i - h_c^2}$ approximately holds as $h_t \approx h_c \ll R_i$ and $20/3\pi \approx 2.12 \approx 2$. Actually, the present indentation results are limited in contact depth to less than 0.5 μm , while the tip radius amounts to 20 μm . We note that the apparently significant differences between Tabor's formulation and the proposal by Pathak and Kalidindi results from their more than doubling the strains as they replace the numerical factor of 0.2 by $4/3\pi \approx 0.42$ when they refer [11,14] to the Tabor strain.

Discrepancies between the CSM indentations done at different strain rates can be due to a detrimental effect of fast straining on the measurement of stiffness. Merle et al. [22] examined the phase shift as a function of indentation depth in constant strain rate dynamic measurements to

provide an indication of possible strain rate effects. For the present CSM results, Fig. 11 shows that, for a strain rate of 0.1 s⁻¹, the phase shift increases above 5° as the displacement into the surface advances to about 200 nm, while at slower strain rates the phase shift remains below about 2°. Even though the phase angle oscillates around 0° for the lowest strain rate tested (0.01 s⁻¹), there is a change in pattern below and above a displacement of about 200 nm, which could be related to the onset of the divergence observed in the ISSC constructed from the stiffness-based contact radius (Fig. 5e, f). A further fine-tuning of the material-dependent optimal parameters used in dynamic nanoindentation is necessary to fully exploit the advantages of CSM mode.

The quality of the surface (roughness, imperfections, polishing-induced residual stresses, ...) and the zero contact point detection strongly affect the initial elastic loading segment in the range of few tens of nm. This affects the extraction of the elastic modulus from the

Fig. 11. Phase angle evolution during room temperature CSM measurements performed at constant strain rate of 0.01, 0.05 and 0.1 s⁻¹.

ISSC, based on near surface measurements, and also contributes to the inaccuracy of the yield stress, besides the constraint factor discussed above. An effective zero-point determination as reported by Kalidindi and Pathak [14] may improve the potential of CSM based derivation of ISSCs and is subject of further investigations.

5. Conclusions

To evaluate tensile properties from nanoindentation test results, the determination of the contact area, the definition of representative stresses and strains, and the fitting to constitutive equations are the important steps, the most adequate choice of which is still matter of discussion and may depend on the instrument, material analysed and testing procedure. In the present work it is shown that the methodology used to determine the contact radius is critical to achieve consistent results. The geometrical definition of the contact radius provides a consistent shape of the ISSC; however it requires a good calibration of the true indenter radius as a function of depth. On the other hand, contact radii determined by Hertz' contact mechanics depend sensitively on the measurement of the stiffness, which is affected by parasitic compliances and, in the case of dynamic measurements, dissipative losses (internal friction) in the oscillator system. Moreover, the Hertz model requires the elastic modulus of the material to be known or derived from the initial loading.

The present nanoindentation in vacuum using tip and sample heating and active surface referencing allowed stable, low drift measurements at high temperatures. Force-displacement curves have been recorded using different quasi-static and dynamic methods. The measurements resulted in closely matching hardness profiles for the different testing methods and were consistent with a hardness decrease by a factor of three from room temperature to 600 °C. Indentation tensile properties of P91 ferritic/martensitic steel have then been extracted from the spherical indentations using four different definitions of the contact radius and strain couples.

Through the systematic study of the protocols to generate local stress–strain curves from nanoindentation it is concluded that Tabor's strain formulation combined with a geometrically-based determination of the contact radius are best suited to extract indentation stress–strain curves from force-displacement recordings. The inferred indentation tensile properties are closest to the actually measured tensile properties of the P91 ferritic/martensitic steel, however, there is a systematic under-estimation of the apparent elastic modulus and yield stresses for all measurement temperatures. This is due to the strain and work hardening dependences of the constraint factor in the elastic-plastic transition range. The values of the ultimate tensile strength, which derive from fitting the indentation stress–strain curves to power-law hardening rules, fit very well for the quasi-static method and the dynamic method with the lowest strain rate, while they are over-estimated for the higher strain rates. This confirms the adequacy of a constant constraint factor $C = 3$ for P91 in the fully plastic range, whereas doubts are created about extending this C value to the yielding of the material.

It has become apparent that dynamic continuous stiffness measurements do not improve results as compared to the quasi-static multicycle measurements. In particular, the determination of the apparent elastic properties (effective modulus) by continuous stiffness measurements at elevated temperatures provided inconsistent results, because there are unresolved issues of dynamic measurements regarding the dependence of results on the sinusoidal excitation parameters, the strain rate of the increasing base load and the impact of averaging procedures applied to the continuous recordings.

Data availability

The raw/processed data required to reproduce these findings cannot be shared at this time due to technical or time limitations.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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